

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

Grant Agreement number 21NRM05

Project short name STASIS

Project full title Standardisation for safe implant scanning in MRI

Data management plan 1st 2nd

Confidentiality status PU - Public, fully open

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1 Data management plan

1.1 Data summary

Questions	Answers
1 Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use them for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.	<p>The project re-used internal data from participants.</p> <p>WP3 utilised three digital models generated and evaluated in the predecessor EMPIR project 17IND01 MIMAS. These models were used to evaluate gradient induced heating activities in this project. The re-used digital models are part of a signed agreement with one project partner that has been extended for the STASIS project. The agreement limits the use of the models to the project.</p>
2 What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?	<p>The project collected:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Images in PNG and JPEG format • Numerical data in CSV • Text descriptions in Markdown • Computer-aided design (CAD) in STEP and STL
3 What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?	<p>The data generated and re-used was from measurements, calibrations, validations, simulations, testing and hardware design files. The data was used to meet the objectives 1-4 of the project and in conference and peer-reviewed publications.</p> <p>Re-used data originated from predecessor EMPIR project 17IND01 MIMAS included three digital models that contributed to meeting objectives 3 and 4. Anatomical human body models carrying orthopaedic passive implants positioned performing a “virtual surgery”. In particular the following models have been adopted throughout the project: Glenn with hip, knee implants and YoonSun with shoulder implant. These digital models are part of a signed agreement that has been extended for the STASIS project. The agreement limits the use of the models to the project and the models cannot be shared publicly.</p> <p>The project generated 11 open-source repositories and 15 datasets. The purpose of the data generation and its relation to the objectives of the project is specified below:</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Open Source Repositories</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Wireless reference implant – Open Source Hardware Repository. Contributed to meeting objectives 1 and 2. https://www.opensourceimaging.org/project/wireless-reference-implant/ 2. 8-channel 3T pTx RF coil – Open Source Hardware Repository. Contributed to meeting objectives 1 and 2. https://www.opensourceimaging.org/project/8-channel-transmit-receive-rf-coil-for-3t/ 3. 8-channel 7T pTx RF coil – Open Source Hardware Repository. Contributed to meeting objectives 1 and 2. https://gitlab1.ptb.de/mri-lab/8ch-ptx-headcoil-7t

	<p>4. Parallel transmission medical implant safety testbed – Open Source Hardware Repository. Contributed to meeting objectives 1 and 2. https://www.opensourceimaging.org/project/ptx-implant-safety-testbed/</p> <p>5. COSI Measure v2 – Open Source Hardware Repository. Contributed to meeting objectives 1 and 2. https://www.opensourceimaging.org/project/cosi-measure/</p> <p>6. NEXUS console – Open Source Hard-/Software Repository. Contributed to meeting objective 2. https://www.opensourceimaging.org/project/nexus-console/</p> <p>7. STASIS RF exposure hardware – Open Source Hardware Repository. Contributed to meeting objective 2. https://github.com/sOrzada/STASIS_Exposure_Hardware</p> <p>8. STASIS RF exposure software – Open Source Software Repository. Contributed to meeting objective 2. https://github.com/sOrzada/STASIS_Control</p> <p>9. IEC/IEEE 62704-1: spatial-average SAR – Open Source Software Repository. Contributed to meeting objectives 3 and 4. https://github.com/umbertozanovello/IEC-IEEE-62704-1-spatial-average-SAR</p> <p>10. Sim4Life-ISO10974_gcHeatingAnalysis – Open Source Software Repository. Contributed to meeting objective 3. https://github.com/umbertozanovello/Sim4Life-ISO10974_gcHeatingAnalysis</p> <p>11. CoSimPy – Open Source Software Repository. Contributed to meeting objective 3. https://umbertozanovello.github.io/CoSimPy/</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Datasets</p> <p>12. Dataset related to article on simultaneous RF and GC electromagnetic fields published in the paper: https://doi.org/10.1002/mrm.70059 . Contributed to meeting objective 3. https://zenodo.org/records/17062126</p> <p>13. Dataset related to article "Gradient-induced vibrations and motion-induced Lenz effects on conductive nonmagnetic orthopedic implants in MRI". Contributed to objective 3. https://zenodo.org/records/12569940</p>
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	<p>14. Dataset related to thermal/power simulations/measurments for GC heating. Contributed to objectives 3 and 4. https://zenodo.org/records/17698731</p> <p>15. Dataset related to article on polynomial chaos expansion of SAR and temperature. Contributed to objectives 3 and 4. https://zenodo.org/records/10972429</p> <p>16. 8-channel 3T parallel transmission RF headcoil - Open Source Hardware. Contributed to meeting objectives 1 and 2. https://zenodo.org/records/17693366</p> <p>17. Control software for STASIS open source RF exposure system - Open Source Software. Contributed to meeting objective 2. https://zenodo.org/records/17693454</p> <p>18. COSI Measure v2 positioning and measurement hardware - Open Source Hardware. Contributed to meeting objectives 1 and 2. https://zenodo.org/records/17693403</p> <p>19. CoSimPy Python electromagnetic cosimulation library – Open Source Software. Contributed to meeting objective 3. https://zenodo.org/records/17705048</p> <p>20. Gradient coil heating analysis for Sim4Life ISO10974 - Open Source Software. Contributed to meeting objective 3. https://zenodo.org/records/17647191</p> <p>21. IEC-IEEE 62704 spatial SAR averaging algorithm - Open Source Software. Contributed to meeting objectives 3 and 4. https://zenodo.org/records/17693488</p> <p>22. NEXUS console for magnetic resonance imaging - Open Source Soft-/Hardware. Contributed to meeting objective 2. https://zenodo.org/records/17693419</p> <p>23. Parallel transmission medical implant safety testbed - Open Source Hardware. Contributed to meeting objectives 1 and 2. https://zenodo.org/records/17693397</p> <p>24. STASIS RF Exposure Hardware for parallel transmission MR safety testing - Open Source Hardware. Contributed to meeting objective 2. https://zenodo.org/records/17693431</p> <p>25. Wireless Reference Implant - Open Source Hardware. Contributed to meeting objectives 1 and 2. https://zenodo.org/records/17693321</p> <p>26. 8-channel 7T parallel transmission RF headcoil - Open Source Hardware. Contributed to meeting objectives 1 and 2. https://zenodo.org/records/17693376</p>
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4 What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?	The overall size of the generated data was approximately 600MB.
5 What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?	<p>All of the new datasets and open-source repositories consisted of data generated through the following measurement techniques and instruments: MRI scanner, commercial and home-built sensor equipment, computer simulations (Sim4Life), and data evaluation models (e.g. Monte Carlo). The data elaboration was performed mainly with the following software: Matlab, Python.</p> <p>The provenance and context of the data were thoroughly documented. The data are accompanied by information on how they were captured, processed, analysed, and validated. Other relevant information was also provided. For Open Source Hardware the relevant standard DIN SPEC 3105 was applied and a certification process started over the conformity assessment body of the non-profit organization Open Source Imaging Initiative e.V..</p> <p>Re-used data originated from predecessor EMPIR project 17IND01 MIMAS included three digital models that contributed to meeting objectives 3 and 4. Anatomical human body models carrying orthopaedic passive implants positioned performing a “virtual surgery”. In particular the following models have been adopted throughout the project: Glenn with hip, knee implants and YoonSun with shoulder implant. These digital models are part of a signed agreement that has been extended for the STASIS project. The agreement limits the use of the models to the project and the models cannot be shared publicly.</p>
6 To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?	<p>The data will be useful to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholders from industry: Implant manufacturers, MR manufacturers, test houses • Standardisation bodies: IEC 62B MT40, ISO TC150, ASTM SC F04.15, IEC TC 106 • Scientific community working in the field of MR safety

1.2 Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR) Data

1.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Questions	Answers
7 Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?	Yes, if applicable, a DOI or commit/tag on Git repositories was used.
8 Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.	The metadata created for all of the project's deposited datasets is open under a CC BY or CC 0 license, in line with the FAIR principles and provide information at least about the following: datasets (description, date of deposit, author(s), venue and embargo); European Partnership on Metrology funding; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the dataset and the authors involved in the action. Where applicable, the metadata includes persistent identifiers for related publications and other research outputs.

9 Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimise the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?	If applicable, the following search keywords are provided in the metadata to optimise the discovery and potential re-use of the deposited datasets: magnetic resonance imaging, MR safety, implant safety, active implantable medical devices (AIMD), RF induced heating, gradient induced heating, wireless communication, open-source hardware, open-source software
10 Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?	Zenodo complies with FAIR principles (https://about.zenodo.org/principles/). The metadata are indexed in a searchable resource. Metadata are licensed under CC0, except for email addresses. All metadata are exported via Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH) and can be harvested.

1.2.2 Making data accessible

Questions	Answers
Repository:	
11 Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?	<p>The data and associated metadata, documentation, hardware designs and was deposited in the trusted open access repository Zenodo (https://zenodo.org), in PTB's Open Access Gitlab Repository (https://gitlab1.ptb.de/) or in any other suitable public repository (Gitlab or Github).</p> <p>The data sets generated so far in the project have been deposited in the following trusted repositories:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Wireless reference implant. https://zenodo.org/records/17693321 2. 8-channel 3T pTx RF coil. https://zenodo.org/records/17693366 3. 8-channel 7T pTx RF coil. https://zenodo.org/records/17693376 4. Parallel transmission implant safety testbed. https://zenodo.org/records/17693397 5. COSI Measure v2. https://zenodo.org/records/17693403 6. NEXUS console. https://zenodo.org/records/17693419 7. STASIS RF exposure hardware. https://zenodo.org/records/17693431 8. STASIS RF exposure software. https://zenodo.org/records/17693454 9. IEC/IEEE 62704-1: spatial-average SAR. https://zenodo.org/records/17693488 10. Sim4Life-ISO10974_gcHeatingAnalysis. https://zenodo.org/records/17647191

Questions	Answers
	<p>11. Dataset related to article on simultaneous RF and GC electromagnetic fields. https://zenodo.org/records/17062126</p> <p>12. Dataset related to article "Gradient-induced vibrations and motion-induced Lenz effects on conductive nonmagnetic orthopedic implants in MRI". https://zenodo.org/records/12569940</p> <p>13. Dataset related to thermal/power simulations/measurments for GC heating. https://zenodo.org/records/17698731</p> <p>14. Dataset related to article on polynomial chaos expansion of SAR and temperature. https://zenodo.org/records/10972429</p> <p>15. CoSimPy. https://zenodo.org/records/17705048</p> <p>The project applies highest open-science practices, because open-source software and open-source hardware designs are shared in publi repositories alongside publications and datasets. Gitlab and Github repositories are mainly used to maintain and advance the projects and facilitate rebuilds and reuse by others. A static, frozen version of these repositories was upload into a static trusted repository in Zenodo according to EURAMET guidance and in order to receive a DOI.</p>
12 Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?	Yes. The identified repository (Zenodo) is already working and correctly label the datasets with a metadata scheme which is compatible with DataCite. Similarly, the workflows of Gitlab and Github repositories are compatible with the envisioned data sharing plan.
13 Does the repository ensure that the data are assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?	Yes, Zenodo will assign an identifier (DOI) to each of the project's deposited datasets. The repository will resolve the identifier to a digital object.
Data:	
14 Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.	<p>Data that is needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications will be made openly available as the default unless thereis a specific reason not to publish the data.</p> <p>Specific reasons include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Very large datasets • Data that compromises the protection of a participant(s) intellectual property • Data obtained with the permission of third parties, but the third parties have not agreed to make the data publicly available. <p>The level of data made available will also be considered, for example, MR raw data will not be provided unless there is a clear reason for doing so.</p>
15 If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual	The data used in scientific publications, posters and oral communications were made available for re-use as soon as is reasonably possible. Most data produced is open-source and no IP

Questions	Answers
property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.	protection was envisioned. In the case of sensitive data, an embargo period of 12 months will be applied whilst a patent application is pending.
16 Will the data be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol?	Yes, Zenodo provides well described conditions for free and standardised access (see http://about.zenodo.org/policies/). Data will be accessible through Zenodo's REST API https://developers.zenodo.org
17 If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?	There are no restrictions on the use of the published data, but users will be required to acknowledge the project and the source of the data (CC-BY 4.0)
18 How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	There is no need to ascertain the identity of persons accessing the data.
19 Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?	This consortium did not have a Data Access Committee, because the project is not going to produce sensitive data. All results are publicly available without restrictions.
Metadata:	
20 Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?	In Zenodo, metadata are licensed under CC0, except for email addresses. All metadata are exported via OAI-PMH and can be harvested.
21 How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data are no longer available?	The data will remain available and findable for the lifetime of the Zenodo repository, which is expected to be a minimum of 20 years. If data are withdrawn from Zenodo, the DOI and the URL of the original object are retained. In case of closure of the Zenodo repository, best efforts will be made by Zenodo to integrate all content into suitable alternative institutional and/or subject based repositories.
22 Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data and will this be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?	The data are in a common format and can be read using widely available software (open source or commercial). Standard publicly available software was used where possible. The projects 15 open-source repositories/datasets which have been deposited in Zenodo i) are accessible using the following software tools, ii) require the following documentation about the software iii) require the following software: 1. Wireless reference implant i) C/C++, FreeCAD, DipTrace ii) Readme available iii) Open

Questions	Answers
	<p>source files deposited on Gitlab/Zenodo</p> <p>2. 8-channel 3T pTx RF coil</p> <p>i) KiCAD, FreeCAD, Autodesk Inventor ii) Readme available iii) Open source files deposited on Gitlab/Zenodo</p> <p>3. 8-channel 7T pTx RF coil</p> <p>i) FreeCAD ii) Readme available iii) Open source files deposited on Gitlab/Zenodo</p> <p>4. Parallel transmission medical implant safety testbed</p> <p>i) C, Fortran, Python ii) Readme available iii) Open source files deposited on Gitlab/Zenodo</p> <p>5. COSI Measure v2</p> <p>i) KiCAD, FreeCAD, Python ii) Readme available iii) Open source files deposited on Gitlab/Zenodo</p> <p>6. NEXUS console</p> <p>i) Python, C ii) Readme available iii) Open source files deposited on Github/Zenodo</p> <p>7. STASIS RF exposure hardware</p> <p>i) KiCAD, Eagle, Spice, Fusion360 ii) Readme available iii) Open source files deposited on Github/Zenodo</p> <p>8. STASIS RF exposure software</p> <p>i) Python ii) Readme available iii) Open source files deposited on Github/Zenodo</p> <p>9. IEC/IEEE 62704-1: spatial-average SAR</p> <p>i) Python ii) Readme available iii) Source code available</p> <p>10. Sim4Life-ISO10974_gcHeatingAnalysis</p> <p>i) Python, Sim4Life ii) Readme available iii) Source code available</p> <p>11. Dataset related to article on simultaneous RF and GC electromagnetic fields</p> <p>i) Matlab ii) Readme file added iii) No software needed</p> <p>12. Dataset related to article "Gradient-induced vibrations and motion-induced Lenz effects on conductive nonmagnetic</p>

Questions	Answers
	<p>orthopedic implants in MRI"</p> <p>i) Excel ii) No specialist software required iii) No other software required</p> <p>13. Dataset related to thermal/power simulations/measurements for GC heating</p> <p>i) Matlab ii) Readme available iii) No other software required</p> <p>14. Dataset related to article on polynomial chaos expansion of SAR and temperature</p> <p>i) Matlab, Excel ii) Readme available iii) No other software required</p> <p>15. CoSimPy</p> <p>i) Python ii) Readme available iii) No other software required</p>

1.2.3 Making data interoperable

Questions	Answers
<p>23 What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?</p>	<p>The datasets are all interoperable, as the chosen metadata scheme is compliant with the recommended standards DataCite and OpenAIRE. The wording was chosen to be compatible with subject-specific vocabularies such as MESH</p>
<p>24 In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow their re-use, refinement or extension?</p>	<p>For all datasets: there was no need for a mapping, since the used terminology was chosen to be compatible with the existing literature.</p>
<p>25 Will your data include qualified references¹ to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?</p>	<p>Yes, the project’s datasets that were deposited in the chosen repository (e.g. Zenodo) might include qualified references to other datasets from the same project or from previous research.</p>

¹ A qualified reference is a cross-reference that explains its intent. For example, X is regulator of Y is a much more qualified reference than X is associated with Y, or X see also Y. The goal therefore is to create as many meaningful links as possible between (meta)data resources to enrich the contextual knowledge about the data. (Source: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/13-metadata-include-qualified-references-metadata/>)

1.2.4 Increase data re-use

Questions	Answers
<p>26 How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?</p>	<p>A short README file (e.g. Markdown) was provided together with the data, in order to enable data analysis and to facilitate data re-use.</p>
<p>27 Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard re-use licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?</p>	<p>All datasets submitted to the trusted repository Zenodo were licensed under a Creative Commons licence (CC-BY 4.0, international). Users will be required to acknowledge the consortium and the source of the data in any resulting publications.</p> <p>The projects 15 datasets/repositories include the following licenses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Wireless reference implant; CERN-OHL-W v2 2. 8-channel 3T pTx RF coil; CERN-OHL-W v2 3. 8-channel 7T pTx RF coil; CERN-OHL-W v2 4. Parallel transmission medical implant safety testbed; CERN-OHL-W v2 5. COSI Measure v2; CERN-OHL-W v2 6. NEXUS console; GPL-v3 7. STASIS RF exposure hardware; CERN-OHL-W 8. STASIS RF exposure software; GPL-v3 9. IEC/IEEE 62704-1: spatial-average SAR; Apache-2.0 10. Sim4Life-ISO10974_gcHeatingAnalysis; MIT License 11. Dataset related to article on simultaneous RF and GC electromagnetic fields; CC-BY 4.0 12. Dataset related to article "Gradient-induced vibrations and motion-induced Lenz effects on conductive nonmagnetic orthopedic implants in MRI"; CC-BY 4.0 13. Dataset related to thermal/power simulations/measurements for GC heating; CC-BY 4.0 14. Dataset related to article on polynomial chaos expansion of SAR and temperature; CC-BY 4.0 15. CoSimPy; MIT Licence

Questions	Answers
<p>28 Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?</p>	<p>Any data published in open-access journals are usable by third parties after the datasets have been deposited in Zenodo. The data that do not relate to peer-reviewed publications were made available for re-use on a case-by-case basis.</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Open Source Repositories</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Wireless reference implant – Open Source Hardware Repository. https://www.opensourceimaging.org/project/wireless-reference-implant/ 2. 8-channel 3T pTx RF coil – Open Source Hardware Repository. https://www.opensourceimaging.org/project/8-channel-transmit-receive-rf-coil-for-3t/ 3. 8-channel 7T pTx RF coil – Open Source Hardware Repository. https://gitlab1.ptb.de/mri-lab/8ch-ptx-headcoil-7t 4. Parallel transmission medical implant safety testbed – Open Source Hardware Repository. https://www.opensourceimaging.org/project/ptx-implant-safety-testbed/ 5. COSI Measure v2 – Open Source Hardware Repository. https://www.opensourceimaging.org/project/cosi-measure/ 6. NEXUS console – Open Source Hard-/Software Repository. https://www.opensourceimaging.org/project/nexus-console/ 7. STASIS RF exposure hardware – Open Source Hardware Repository. https://github.com/sOrzada/STASIS_Exposure_Hardware 8. STASIS RF exposure software – Open Source Software Repository. https://github.com/sOrzada/STASIS_Control 9. IEC/IEEE 62704-1: spatial-average SAR – Open Source Software Repository. https://github.com/umbertozanovello/IEC-IEEE-62704-1-spatial-average-SAR 10. Sim4Life-ISO10974_gcHeatingAnalysis – Open Source Software Repository. https://github.com/umbertozanovello/Sim4Life-ISO10974_gcHeatingAnalysis 11. CoSimPy – Open Source Software Repository. https://umbertozanovello.github.io/CoSimPy/ <p style="text-align: center;">Datasets</p>

Questions	Answers
	<p>12. Dataset related to article on simultaneous RF and GC electromagnetic fields published in the paper: https://doi.org/10.1002/mrm.70059 . https://zenodo.org/records/17062126</p> <p>13. Dataset related to article "Gradient-induced vibrations and motion-induced Lenz effects on conductive nonmagnetic orthopedic implants in MRI". https://zenodo.org/records/12569940</p> <p>14. Dataset related to thermal/power simulations/measurements for GC heating. https://zenodo.org/records/17698731</p> <p>15. Dataset related to article on polynomial chaos expansion of SAR and temperature. https://zenodo.org/records/10972429</p> <p>16. 8-channel 3T parallel transmission RF headcoil - Open Source Hardware. https://zenodo.org/records/17693366</p> <p>17. Control software for STASIS open source RF exposure system - Open Source Software. https://zenodo.org/records/17693454</p> <p>18. COSI Measure v2 positioning and measurement hardware - Open Source Hardware. https://zenodo.org/records/17693403</p> <p>19. CoSimPy Python electromagnetic cosimulation library – Open Source Software. https://zenodo.org/records/17705048</p> <p>20. Gradient coil heating analysis for Sim4Life ISO10974 - Open Source Software. https://zenodo.org/records/17647191</p> <p>21. IEC-IEEE 62704 spatial SAR averaging algorithm - Open Source Software. https://zenodo.org/records/17693488</p> <p>22. NEXUS console for magnetic resonance imaging - Open Source Software/Hardware. https://zenodo.org/records/17693419</p> <p>23. Parallel transmission medical implant safety testbed - Open Source Hardware. https://zenodo.org/records/17693397</p> <p>24. STASIS RF Exposure Hardware for parallel transmission MR safety testing - Open Source Hardware. https://zenodo.org/records/17693431</p> <p>25. Wireless Reference Implant - Open Source Hardware. https://zenodo.org/records/17693321</p> <p>26. 8-channel 7T parallel transmission RF headcoil - Open Source Hardware. https://zenodo.org/records/17693376</p>

Questions	Answers
29 Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?	Yes, the provenance and context of the data will be thoroughly documented. Data were accompanied by information on how they were captured, processed, analysed, and validated. Other information that enables interpretation and use was also provided.
30 Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.	Data quality assurance was performed through: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Repeated and comparison measurements • Metrological characterisation of the measurement set-ups • Validation of the data collected • Peer-review of publications based on the data
31 Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.	The costs for making the data and research outputs FAIR were covered by each participant, where FAIR principles are already implemented on institutional level. Deposition in public repositories provided additional security, where multiple replicas in a distributed file system were being used. This project did not generate sensitive other research outputs. Information relating to other research outputs collected by the consortium at commercial sites were not shared without the site owner's explicit consent. Information relating to other research outputs acquired from third parties, e.g., manufacturers, were shared without their explicit consent.

1.3 Other research outputs

Questions	Answers
32 In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).	The projects 15 datasets/open-source soft-/hardware repositories include the following licenses: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Wireless reference implant; CERN-OHL-W v2 2. 8-channel 3T pTx RF coil; CERN-OHL-W v2 3. 8-channel 7T pTx RF coil; CERN-OHL-W v2 4. Parallel transmission medical implant safety testbed; CERN-OHL-W v2 5. COSI Measure v2; CERN-OHL-W v2 6. NEXUS console; GPL-v3 7. STASIS RF exposure hardware; CERN-OHL-W 8. STASIS RF exposure software; GPL-v3 9. IEC/IEEE 62704-1: spatial-average SAR; Apache-2.0 10. Sim4Life-ISO10974_gcHeatingAnalysis; MIT License 11. Dataset related to article on simultaneous RF and GC electromagnetic fields; CC-BY 4.0 12. Dataset related to article "Gradient-induced vibrations and motion-induced Lenz effects on conductive nonmagnetic

Questions	Answers
	<p>orthopedic implants in MRI"; CC-BY 4.0</p> <p>13. Dataset related to thermal/power simulations/measurements for GC heating; CC-BY 4.0</p> <p>14. Dataset related to article on polynomial chaos expansion of SAR and temperature; CC-BY 4.0</p> <p>15. CoSimPy; MIT License</p> <p>In addition the following projects were submitted to open source conformity assessment body of the Open Source Imaging Initiative (OSI²) e.V. to receive OSI² attestation (https://www.opensourceimaging.org/) for the open-source documentation (includes attestation according to DIN SPEC 3501 and OSHWA):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. CoSimPy; OSI² Tier 3 attestation received. 2. COSI Measure v2; OSI² Tier 2 attestation received. 3. STASIS RF Exposure Hardware; [Under review] 4. STASIS RF Exposure Software; [Under review]
33 Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.	Current best practices were applied for the documentation of software (opensource.org) and hardware (DIN SPEC 3105-1 and DIN SPEC 3105-2).

1.4 Allocation of resources

Questions	Answers
34 What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.) ?	<p>The costs for making the data and research outputs FAIR were covered by each participant, where FAIR principles are already implemented on institutional level. There were no additional storage/preservation and curation costs within the projects budget.</p> <p>These costs were kept to a minimum by using a free repository (Zenodo) and by making only relevant data and other outputs FAIR</p>
35 How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the European partnership on metrology grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions).	The costs for making the data and research outputs FAIR were covered by each participant, where FAIR principles are already implemented on institutional level. Long term preservation was ensured by depositing the data within repositories (Zenodo, PTB's Open Access Repository). There were no costs associated with the long-term preservation of the data in these repositories.

36 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?	Each participant was responsible for data management of the corresponding activities. Each participant was responsible for organising data backup and storage, data archiving and for depositing the data within the repositories (Zenodo, Gitlab, Github, PTB's Open Access Repository)
37 How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?	Long term preservation was ensured by depositing the data within repositories (Zenodo, Gitlab, Github, PTB's Open Access Repository). There were no project costs associated with the long-term preservation of the data in these repositories. The data will increase in value over time because of its fundamental impact in a wide range of applications. It will enable the technologies developed in the project to be taken up by the standards bodies.

1.5 Data security

Questions	Answers
38 What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?	<p>During the project, data was automatically saved daily on work computer, server in the work unit, laboratory computer. Backups were performed daily.</p> <p>Data recovery and secure storage. The participants stored data on their organisations' networks, which are protected by firewall, backups etc. Data were also stored in the project's cloud environment, with password protected login.</p> <p>Deposition in the Zenodo public repository provided additional security as it has multiple replicas in a distributed file system which is backed up on a nightly basis.</p> <p>Transfer of sensitive data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This project did not generate sensitive data.
39 Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?	<p>Yes, the data will be safely stored in the Zenodo open access repository. Zenodo and the underlying Invenio Framework for digital repositories were designed according to the Open Archival Information Systems (OAIS) reference model.</p> <p>Other data will be safely stored on the institutional repository situated on two physically and geographically separated servers, which are regularly backed up. The repository is engaging to obtain a DINI certification.</p>

1.6 Ethics

Questions	Answers
40 Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics report(s) and the ethics section in the Annex 1.	There were no ethical or legal issues.
41 Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term	The project did not deal with personal data.

Questions	Answers
preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?	

1.7 Other issues

Questions	Answers
42 Do you, or will you, make use of other national / funder / sectorial / departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?	<p>Data management was compliant with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The research data policy of the European Partnership on Metrology; • European laws about data security and the protection of privacy (e.g. GDPR); <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutional guidelines; • Scientific community guidelines.

2 Open science: research data management

Statement	Put an X in the box to confirm	Or, list any exceptions to this
All participants have adhered to the requirements of the project's GA and CA with respect to open science: research data management (GA Article 17 and its Annex 5) for this reporting period	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

